

CORDEX-FPS AEROSOL PROTOCOL 1B

CORDEX SCENARIO RUNS WITH or WITHOUT EVOLVING AEROSOL FORCINGS

Version 0: 23 March 2018, S. Somot, P. Nabat, F. Solmon, M. Mallet, available [here](#)

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1. Introduction

The Med-CORDEX Flagship Pilot Study (FPS) aerosol is one of the FPS endorsed by CORDEX in 2016 [\[ADD LINK HERE\]](#). It targets to study the role of the aerosols in shaping the regional climate of the Euro-Mediterranean region. To reach its scientific objectives, various experimental protocols have been proposed to the RCM community.

More specifically, the protocol 1B described below targets to assess the role of the regional aerosol load in the future evolution of the regional climate. It can be seen as a sensitivity experiment to assess current practices in RCM in CORDEX. Indeed, currently, the aerosol forcing and its evolution in historical and scenario runs is not specified in the CORDEX experimental protocol. This creates inconsistencies in the way it is applied in the CORDEX RCMs with potential impacts on the simulated climate change signal. For example for the Med-CORDEX or Euro-CORDEX domains, most of the models do not use evolving aerosols in RCP historical and scenario runs (see Nabat et al. 2015a for Med-CORDEX and Gutiérrez et al. 2020, for Euro-CORDEX).

2. Existing simulations

The protocol proposed here relies on existing CORDEX simulations following the official CORDEX protocol for Med-CORDEX or Euro-CORDEX, whatever the spatial resolution:

- One simulation covering at least the period 1971-2000 for the historical run
- A second simulation covering the period 2021-2050 for the RCP8.5 run

Both simulations are required with some classical variable outputs. We also request from the participating groups to document the way they specify the aerosol in their model runs for CORDEX including a description of the spatio-temporal variability of this forcing. You can follow this example [\[ADD LINK HERE\]](#).

We also request the participating groups to provide their AOD (Aerosol Optical Depth) in netcdf (monthly-mean files) if any as well as radiative characteristics of their aerosols if possible (single scattering albedo, asymmetry parameter, angstrom exponent).

Note that only RCMs including an aerosol forcing can participate to this modelling exercise. This forcing can however be very simple (as in RCA), no need for a complex scheme. This may exclude models such as some versions of WRF and of RegCM

3. Proposed new sensitivity run

For this protocol, it is requested to run an additional future scenario runs of 30 years (2021-2050) that is a perfect twin of the CORDEX standard run. Two options are proposed depending on the aerosol forcing applied in the standard CORDEX runs

Option 1: If you already have evolving aerosols in the scenario runs (such as in RACMO or ALADIN)

Take the AOD of the historical period, average it over the 30 years keeping its spatial and seasonal/monthly variability and apply it to the 2021-2050 period. The goal is to have the same mean AOD in the historical and scenario 30-year period.

Option 2: If you do not have evolving aerosols in the scenario runs (such as in RCA, PROMES, REMO, some WRF versions, HIRHAM, COSMO-CLM)

CNRM (contact pierre.nabat[at]meteo.fr) will provide you an AOD anomaly adapted to your model configuration to be added to your presente-climate AOD forcing. You will have to run the 2021-2050 period with the modified AOD forcing. This AOD forcing comes from a GCM with interactive aerosols and participating to the ACCMIP initiative (LMDZ-INCA, Szopa et al. 2013). It is the forcing applied in CNRM-ALADIN runs forced by the CNRM-CM5 GCM.

4. Run and file naming

The following simulations are requested:

- **HIS1B** (1971-2000) a historical simulation (existing in Euro-CORDEX or Med-CORDEX)
- **SCE1B** (2021-2050) RCP8.5 simulation (existing in Euro-CORDEX or Med-CORDEX)
- **AER1B** (2021-2050) RCP8.5 simulation with a different aerosol evolution (new simulation)

Please contact Pierre Nabat (pierre.nabat[at]meteo.fr) to get an evolution of aerosols adapted to your model configuration for simulation AER1B. These simulations have to be run with a regional climate model on a domain including the Med-CORDEX official domain (see details [here](#)), the Euro-CORDEX official domain being therefore accepted (see details [here](#)).

Example of naming for the output files:

- Existing CORDEX run:
`rsds_EUR-11_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_rcp85_r1i1p1_CNRM-ALADIN63_v1_mon_202101-203012.nc`
- if option1:
`rsds_EUR-11_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_rcp85_r1i1p1_CNRM-ALADIN63_v1cstaer_mon_202101-203012.nc`
- if option2:
`rsds_EUR-11_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_rcp85_r1i1p1_CNRM-ALADIN63_v1evoaer_mon_202101-203012.nc`

5. Variables to be stored (priority list, netcdf, CMOR-like)

Variables	Long names	Units	Freq.	Comment
clt	Total Cloud Fraction	%	mon, day	
hfls	Surface Upward Latent Heat Flux	W.m-2	mon, day	
hfss	Surface Upward Sensible Heat Flux	W.m-2	mon, day	
pr	Precipitation	kg.m-2.s-1	mon, day	
psl	Sea Level Pressure	hPa	mon, day	
rlds	Surface downwelling longwave radiation	W.m-2	mon, day	
rldscs	Clear-sky surface downwelling longwave radiation	W.m-2	mon, day	Not a CORDEX variable yet
rsds	Surface downwelling shortwave radiation	W.m-2	mon, day	
rsdscs	Clear-sky surface downwelling shortwave radiation	W.m-2	mon, day	Not a CORDEX variable yet
sfcWind	Near-surface wind speed	m.s-1	mon, day	
tas	Near-surface Air Temperature	K	mon, day	
ts	Surface Temperature	K	mon	
uas	Eastward Near-Surface Wind	m.s-1	mon, day	
vas	Northward Near-Surface Wind	m.s-1	mon, day	
hus	Specific humidity	kg.m-2.s-1	mon	P19
ta	Temperature	K	mon	P19
zg	Geopotential Height	m	mon	P19
od550aer	Total aerosol optical depth at 550 nm	1	mon	Not a CORDEX variable yet
od550dust	ust aerosol optical depth at 550 nm	1	mon	Not a CORDEX variable yet
od550oa	organic matter aerosol	1	mon	Not a CORDEX variable yet

	optical depth at 550 nm			
od550so4	sulfate aerosol optical depth at 550 nm	1	mon	Not a CORDEX variable yet
od550soa	secondary organic aerosol optical depth at 550 nm	1	mon	Not a CORDEX variable yet
od550ss	sea salt aerosol optical depth at 550 nm	1	mon	Not a CORDEX variable yet
P19: list of the 19 pressure vertical levels in hPa: 1000, 975, 950, 925, 900, 850, 800, 750, 700, 650, 600, 550, 500, 450, 400, 350, 300, 250, 200				

6. Participating groups and status of the runs

Institute	Contact person	GCM RCM	Run status
AUTH	katragou[at]auth.gr vapavid[at]physics.auth.gr	CESM1-CAM5 WRF	done
CNRM	pierre.nabat[at]meteo.fr	CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1 ALADIN63	done
CNRM	pierre.nabat[at]meteo.fr	NorESM-M ALADIN63	done
CNRM	pierre.nabat[at]meteo.fr	MPI-ESM-LR ALADIN63	done
CNRM	pierre.nabat[at]meteo.fr	HadGEM2-ES ALADIN63	done
ETHZ	silje.soerland[at]env.ethz.ch	MPI-ESM-LR COSMO-crCLM	done
GERICS	joni-pekka.pietikainen[at]hzg.de	EC-EARTH REMO2015	done
KNMI	vanmeijg[at]knmi.nl	EC-EARTH RACMO22E	done
LA	fabien.solmon[at]aero.obs-mip.fr	EC-EARTH RegCM	done

7. References

Gutiérrez C., Somot S., Nabat P., Mallet M., Corre L., van Meijgaard E., Perpiñán O., Gaertner M.A. (2020) Future evolution of surface solar radiation and photovoltaic potential in Europe: investigating the role of aerosols. *Environ. Res. Lett.*, 15 (3), 034035, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ab6666>

Nabat, P., Somot, S., Mallet, M., Sevault, F., Chiacchio, M., & Wild, M. (2015). Direct and semi-direct aerosol radiative effect on the Mediterranean climate variability using a coupled regional climate system model. *Climate dynamics*, 44(3-4), 1127-1155. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-014-2205-6>

Szopa, S., Balkanski, Y., Schulz, M., Bekki, S., Cugnet, D., Fortems-Cheiney, A., ... & Idelkadi, A. (2013). Aerosol and ozone changes as forcing for climate evolution between 1850 and 2100. *Climate dynamics*, 40(9-10), 2223-2250, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-012-1408-y>